

INFLUENCE OF ORGANOCLAYS ON CREEP AND IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF THERMOPLASTICS

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SUMMARY

Microstructure and mechanical properties of polypropylene and polyamide 6 nanocomposite with filler on the base organoclay was investigated. Results of a microstructure assessment, creep and impact testing are presented in the paper.

Keywords: nanocomposite, creep, impact properties

INTRODUCTION

Nanocomposites represent important potential for formation novel group of construction materials for higher levels of service loading [1,2]. In comparison with conventional composites, nanocomposites achieve similar properties (stiffness, strength, hardness, thermal conductivity, shape stability, barrier properties) with small content of a nanofiller (1 – 10 vol. %), due to their great interface between nanoparticles and matrix. However development of organoclay nanocomposites demonstrates their considerable embrittlement notably during impact loading.

EXPERIMENTS

Materials

Two types of matrix were used for experiments. First, polypropylene has non-polar character of lateral units, second matrix is polyamide 6 with polar character of amide groups. Reinforcing phase is clay on the base montmorillonite (MMT) modified by quarter ammonium salt. Samples for mechanical testing was prepared by injection moulding.

Testing methods

Properties of nanocomposites and neat polymers were compared in all cases. Tension properties, creep tension properties, Charpy notched impact strength, puncture impact behavior and modified creep test in surfactant (ESC) were conducted on tested materials.

RESULTS

Figure 1. Puncture impact behaviour of neat PA6 and PA6/MMT

Figure 2. Stress dependence of creep rate at $\epsilon=2\%$

Neat PA6 has got high toughness at multiaxis impact loading. PA6/MMT absorbed higher quanta of energy in state of crack initiation, however complete energy absorbed to puncture is determined only by energy to crack initiation and after reach a maximum force, the brittle crack grows unstably, figure 1.

Creep rate of both materials depend on applied stress by Norton's law, figure 2. Results on this graph obviously show improving influence of MMT to creep resistance, neat PA6 creeps more then two orders of magnitude faster than PA6/MMT nanocomposite under all loading conditions.

CONCLUSION

Nanocomposites prepared with montmorillonite show improved strength, modulus, creep properties, barrier properties and etc. Significant drawback is their low fracture toughness, which greatly limited their engineering application. Immobilisation of polymer chains by rigid particle improves stiffness, but particles hinder of development of a plastic deformation, which absorb fracture energy.

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References

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